

Thyroid dysfunction in chronic kidney disease patients

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Thyroid dysfunction is seen in chronic kidney disease patients. It is caused due to multifactorial causes as both kidney disease and thyroid dysfunction are interrelated. In early stages of renal disease due to loss of protein thyroid hormones bounded to proteins lost in urine latter there may be suppression of thyroid axis due to accumulation of various toxins and inflammatory mediators on hypothalamus-pituitary axis. **Material and Methods:** This study was comprise of 100 patients conducted in G.R.Medical College. Thyroid hormones levels were compared among and correlated with various stages of kidney disease. **Observation:** Most common thyroid dysfunction seen was low tt3 or tt4 with normal tsh pattern .As the stages of chronic kidney disease progress the thyroid dysfunction increases. The values of total t3 and total t4 increases as the stage progress and tsh values decrease as the stage progress .overt hypothyroidism was seen in advanced chronic kidney disease stage. **Conclusion:** Thyroid dysfunction significantly increases as the ckd stage progress. Thyroid hormone test should be included in routine investigation in chronic kidney disease patients as symptoms of thyroid dysfunction and uraemia frequency overlap leading to overlooked this condition.

Keywords: *Thyroid dysfunction, chronic kidney disease, hormones*

INTRODUCTION:

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is serious health problem the number of people with impaired renal function is rapidly rising due to associated comorbidities such as type 2 diabetes, hypertension and Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) [1]. Progression of CKD is associated with having a Number of complications, including thyroid dysfunction, dyslipidaemia and CVD leading to further impact in quality of life. CKD affects the thyroid hormones in various ways. This relation is bilateral as one affect other one. The protein that transport the largest amount of thyroid hormones is thyroxine binding globulin 54kDa mainly produced in liver. The other two proteins with role in transport are transthyretin and albumin Transthyretin has a molecular weight of 55kDa and albumin 66.5kDa all these proteins are normally not detected in urine. When glomerular damage occur there is non selective loss of serum proteins, it causes significant loss of thyroid hormones binding proteins. Along with loss of thyroid hormones binding proteins there is loss of thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3) from body leading to denovo hypothyroidism or increase the requirement of levothyroxine in subjects with pre-existing

hypothyroidism that is already taking treatment. In subjects with proteinuria >3g /day levels of total t4 in urine 24.3ug/day compared to 1.5 ug /day in normal subjects[2]. In uraemia, the pituitary receptor response to TRH is blunted causing decrease in TSH release And a response of TSH to TRH is delayed Because of the decreased clearance and the increase of half-life of TSH.[16] CKD affects the hypothalamus-pituitary thyroid axis And the peripheral metabolism of thyroid hormone. Decrease Gfr causes inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin 1 and TNF alpha get reduced causing reduced expression of type 1 deiodinase causing reduced conversion from T4 to T3 and Since rT3 Is metabolized By 5' Deiodination, its clearance is also reduced. Thus, decreased clearance rather Than increased production is the major basis for increased rT3 [3]. Also there is reduced iodine clearance causing hypothyroidism (Wolff-Chaikoff effect) .Low T3 is the most common laboratory finding and subclinical Hypothyroidism is most common thyroid disorder found in CKD patients [4].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It is Observational Study carried out in department of medicine in J.A group of hospitals Gwalior. Study

Include outdoor and indoor patients confirmed to have Chronic kidney disease. The study comprise 100 patients of Chronic Kidney Disease patients of age above 18 with GFR < 90ml/min/1.73m² for at least 3 months. Patients with Known case of hypothyroidism, Any drugs intake which affect thyroid function, Pregnancy, disease which can affect protein level and Medications affecting thyroid were excluded from study . In all cases written consent was obtained from each subject. All patients were undergone a detailed clinical examination at admission. Relevant history was taken and physical examination including symptom and Signs of Kidney failure was checked followed by hormonal assessment. All the dates were entered in a data collection sheet in an Excel format and analysed using SPSS Software. Numerical values were reported using Mean and standard deviation. Expected range of TT3 is 70-204 ng/dl, expected range of TT4 is 4.5-11microgm/dl and expected ranges of Values of TSH is 0.5-4.5mU/L. P <0.05 was considered to Be statistically significant

RESULTS:

Out of Total number of 100 cases 65 were males and 35 were females.71 cases from stage V, 15 cases from stage IV, 14 cases from stage III.

DISTRIBUTION OF CKD STAGES AS PER ASSOCIATED CORMOBITIES.

Comorbidities	Stage III	Stage IV	Stage V
Diabetes	1	0	9
Hypertension	1	5	5
Diabetes with hypertension	4	4	35
Others	8	6	22

Relationship between CKD stages and blood parameters

	CKD III		CKD IV		CKD V		F	P
	mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Egfr	42.85	5.972	18.46	3.522	9.098	3.038	510.4	0.000
Cr	1.81	0.258	3.753	0.670	7.129	2.791	35.82	0.000
Tt3	78.82	39.96	59.43	21.97	53.33	28.47	3.193	0.045
Tt4	7.08	6.660	5.284	2.137	4.567	2.719	3.431	0.036
Tsh	4.88	4.196	6.156	4.521	6.053	5.514	0.384	0.681

Serum creatinine and egfr increases as we progress from stage 3 to Stage 5 Mean value for Serum creatinine 1.81 ±0.2584, 3.7533 ±0.6607 ,7.129±2.7915 for stage 3,4,5 respectively .mean value for efr 42.857±5.972, 18.466±3.5226, 9.098± 3.0386 respectively for stages 3 ,4,5. Serum Creatinine and Egfr value increases as stage of chronic kidney disease Increases .Serum total t3 value decreases as the kidney stage progress from stage 3 to 5 Mean total t3 value 78.92 ±39.962 ,59.431±21.9729, 53.33 ±28.47 for

Distribution of patients based on dialysis

Stages of ckd	Dialysis	No dialysis	Total cases
Stage III	0	14	14
Stage IV	3	12	15
Stage V	71	0	71

Distribution of thyroid dysfunction as per chronic kidney disease stages

	III	IV	V	Total
Low tt3 or tt4	0	2	25	27
Subclinical hypothyroidism	2	8	13	23
Overt hypothyroidism	0	0	3	3
Hyperthyroidism	1	0	0	1
Euthyroidism	11	5	30	46
Total cases	14	15	71	100

Distribution of thyroid dysfunction out of total 100 cases 46 are euthyroid And 54 has thyroid dysfunction .Maximum thyroid dysfunction was low t3 and t4 syndrome 27% cases .After that subclinical hypothyroidism in 23% cases. Out of total Low 3 or low with normal tsh 10(37%) are male 17 are female (62%).Out of total subclinical hypothyroidism Male are 16 (69%) female are 7 (21%).Overt hypothyroidism has 3 cases all are stage 5. Out of which 1 is Male 2 Females. In stage 5 low t3 or t4 was 35 percent as Compared to 13 percent in stage 4 and zero percent in stage 3. The number Of subclinical hypothyroidism was 13 in stage 5 as compared to stage 4 (8 Cases) percent wise the subclinical hypothyroidism increases as Stage progressed from stage 4 to stage 5. Overt hypothyroidism cases were 3(4%) in stage 5 as compared to stage 3 and stage 4 which has zero percent .Chi-square =27.074 P value is 0.0000 significant <0.05. As the ckd stage advances the thyroid dysfunction prevalence increases.

stages 3 ,4,5 respectively. In our study as stage of chronic kidney disease progress total t3 value decreases. Serum total t4 value decreases as the kidney stage progress from stage 3 to 5.mean t4 value 7.0814±6.6605, 5.284 ± 2.1373, 4.657±2.7192 for stages 3 ,4,5, respectively .serum total t4 value decreases as chronic kidney disease stage progress from Stage 3 to 5 . Mean tsh value 4.8807 ±4.1965, 6.5167± 4.5219, 6.053± 5.5148 for stages 3, 4, 5

respectively. Serum tsh value increases as stages chronic kidney disease progress.

Relationship between creatinine clearance and total T3, free T4 and TSH

Parameter	R value	P value
Tt3	0.35	<0.05
Tt4	0.276	<0.05
Tsh	-0.1089	0.2848

Serum t 3 and t4 shows positive correlation with Egfr as the with p Value significant .serum tsh shows negative correlation.

DISCUSSION:

In our study 100 patients with chronic kidney disease were studied. Patients were examined from 14 year and above. Mean age was 47 year. Maximum age was 84 year Minimum was 18 year. Maximum patients are from age above 60 year. Of the patients distribution as per ckd stages, 71 were from ckd stage 5,15 from Ckd stage 4 ,and 14 were from ckd stage 3. Stage II and stage I ckd patients Were not in study . The most common comorbidity associated was Diabetes with hypertension. Out of total 100 cases thyroid abnormality was found in 54 cases Euthyroid was present in 46 cases. In our study most common thyroid Abnormality seen was low t3 or t4 with normal tsh 27 cases. Subclinical Hypothyroidism was found in 23 cases and overt hypothyroidism was seen in 3 cases. On comparing all stages from stage 3 to stage 5 mean Egfr decrease as the stage of Ckd advances. It was 42.82 in Stage III, 18.46 in stage IV and 9.9 in stage V. Mean Creatinine value increases From stage III to stage V . it was 1.181 in stage 3 and 7.129 in stage V . Mean total t3 Value decreases from stage III to stage V. Mean total t3 in stage III was 78.92, in stage IV it was 59.43 and in stage V it was 53.33 this was statistically Significant. Mean total t4 value also decrease from stage III to stage V Mean total t4 in stage 3 it was 7.08 in stage IV value was 5.284 and in stage V Mean value was 4.567. This was also found statistically significant. Mean Tsh value increases as progress from stage III to stage V .mean Tsh value in stage III was 4.88 compare to in stage V which has mean value of 6.053. This was not statistically significant. As the most common Thyroid dysfunction associated was low tt3 or tt4 with normal Tsh syndrome. Out of total 27 cases maximum were from stage V (25 cases) followed by stage IV (2 cases). With subclinical hypothyroidism maximum cases were from stage V (13 cases) followed by Stage IV (8 cases) followed by stage III (2 cases). Also overt hypothyroidism all cases were from stage V. All these changes were statistically significant. Study conducted By Victoria et al[5]The commonest form of thyroid dysfunction as with Our study was sick euthyroid syndrome (23%) followed by subclinical Hypothyroidism (14%). There was a progressive increase in the prevalence of Thyroiddysfunction from 0% in stage I to 54.5% in stage V. But as compared to our study it was not statistically significant. study

conducted by punekar et al [6] in contrast to our study here overt Hypothyroidism was most common abnormality seen followed by low t3 or T4 syndrome. With the increasing severity of CKD , Overt Hypothyroidism Also increase from stage III to stage V. Ershad et [7] compared the t3 t4 tsh with various stages of chronic Kidney diseases similar to our study they found decreasing trend in t3 t4 with Increase in stage in chronic kidney disease. Tsh level was increased with the Increasing stage of chronic kidney disease. Decreasing t3 t4 was significant But increasing Tsh was not significant similar to our study. Priyanka et al [8]conducted the study they compared the thyroid Profile between less severe vs more severe effected ckd patients , they found The decrease in fT3, fT4 and increase in TSH were more pronounced in Advanced CKD patients. This was consistent with our study. Saroj et al [9] conducted the study over 360 ckd patients in them Thyroid dysfunction Was found in 38.6 % CKD patients, the most common Thyroid dysfunction in contrast to our study was subclinical hypothyroidism. Subclinical Hypothyroidism got significantly Common with CKD progression. Akhil Chandran et al[10] conducted a study where in contrast to our Study they found no significant difference in mean t3 ,t4 tsh value among Various ckd stages . No significant association was found between various Stages of CKD and Tt4, Tsh Values.

LIMITATIONS:

It was single centre study with Most of ckd patients were from stage V. Many of them were already on dialysis since 1 to 2 years and also associated with multiple comorbidities. Stage 1 and 2 were not present in study.

CONCLUSION:

Thyroid dysfunction is a common but under recognized complication Among chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients, including those With end stage renal disease (ESRD) receiving treatment with dialysis[11].Possibly due to overlap of its Accompanying signs and symptoms with those of uraemia (e.g., fatigue, depression, impaired Cognition, impaired physical Function).thyroid function test may changes due To Underlying illness rather than primary thyroid disease this may lead to overlooked thyroid

dysfunction. Thyroid Hormone deficiency may lead to cardiovascular Risk factors that may be particularly relevant to CKD and ESRD patients. As dialysis patients suffer from higher Rates of impaired physical and mental health, thyroid dysfunction is a modifiable risk factor for adverse patient-centred outcomes (e.g., impaired HRQOL(health related quality of life), decreased physical function (12) hence thyroid function test should be included in investigation.

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